

Research Paper

Religion and Politics in Nigeria: A Study of the 2023 Presidential Election

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ABSTRACT: The paper investigated religion and politics in Nigeria with emphasis on the 2023 presidential election. Nigeria is widely recognised as a deeply divided society, structured along multiple and overlapping cleavages such as ethnicity, region, geopolitical zones, and religion. These fault lines profoundly shape political behaviour and competition. Consequently, the mobilisation of ethnic or religious identities as pathways to political power often assumes a sectarian character, with serious implications for the legitimacy, acceptance, and national appeal of candidates who emerge through such processes. The objectives of the study were to examine the dynamics, conduct, and outcomes of the 2023 Presidential election in Nigeria; and analyse the role and impact of religion on voter behaviour, elite mobilisation, and electoral outcomes during the 2023 Presidential election in Nigeria. The study adopted the elite theory propounded by Robert Michel, Gaetano Mosca and Vilfredo Pareto. The study was based entirely on secondary sources of data. Data were obtained from official records of the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) and documented materials from registered political parties in Nigeria. In addition, relevant information was drawn from scholarly books, academic journals, magazines, and other credible published materials. The study concluded that the present political arrangement does not appear to have made room for fair representation by the six geo-political zones in the office of the President of Nigeria. Religion, as in times past, will shape the build-up to and outcome of the 2027 Presidential elections. The risk of States and geopolitical zones voting along sectarian lines is high. This may, however, lead to heightened religious sensitivities that may escalate existing tensions and fragilities. The study recommended that government and civil society organisations should intensify voter education campaigns that emphasise the importance of competence, policies, and national unity over religious affiliation when choosing leaders.

Keywords: Religion, politics, election, presidential, elite

I. Introduction

Nigeria is often portrayed as a profoundly fragmented state in which critical political issues are persistently and, at times, violently contested along intricate ethnic, religious, and regional fault lines (Smyth & Robinson, 2001). The country's dense network of politically salient identities, coupled with a long history of recurrent and seemingly intractable conflicts, justifies its classification as one of the most deeply divided states on the African continent (Osaghae & Suberu, 2005). From its very formation as a colonial entity, Nigeria has grappled with an enduring crisis of territorial and state legitimacy. This legitimacy deficit has repeatedly undermined efforts at fostering national integration, democratic consolidation, political stability, and sustainable economic development (Maier, 2000). The culmination of this legitimacy crisis was arguably the Nigerian Civil War of the late 1960s, which erupted barely a decade after independence in 1960. Although the war ended in 1970, the underlying structural tensions were never fully resolved. Rather than diminishing, patterns of conflict re-emerged and intensified, particularly

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following Nigeria's transition from military to civilian rule in 1999. Since then, the country has witnessed a marked escalation in communal, religious, and political conflicts across different regions.

Nigeria is a religiously plural society in which citizens are constitutionally guaranteed the freedom to practice any religion of their choice, whether Islam, Christianity, or African Traditional Religion. Religion has historically occupied a central place in human society, stemming from humanity's innate inclination toward worship and the search for meaning. This universal impulse has produced a rich mosaic of beliefs, values, attitudes, and rituals, making religion a pervasive and enduring social institution across cultures and civilisations. In the Nigerian context, however, religion has become deeply intertwined with politics, particularly since the return to democratic governance in 1999. Electoral politics in Nigeria have increasingly reflected ethnic and religious considerations. For instance, the 1999 presidential election featured two leading candidates from the Yoruba ethnic group, both of whom were Christians, with Muslim running mates. Similarly, in the 2007 elections, major political parties such as the People's Democratic Party (PDP) and the Action Congress carefully balanced their presidential tickets by pairing Muslim candidates from the North with Christian running mates from the South. This pattern of ethno-religious balancing persisted in the 2011, 2015, and 2019 presidential elections, underscoring the high level of sensitivity attached to Nigeria's ethnic and religious diversity. These arrangements reflected an informal but widely accepted political norm aimed at promoting inclusivity and managing the country's pluralism. However, this convention was significantly challenged during the 2023 presidential election when the ruling All Progressives Congress (APC) presented a same-faith ticket comprising a Muslim presidential candidate and a Muslim vice-presidential candidate, despite widespread public opposition. The decision to field a Muslim–Muslim ticket departed sharply from established political practice and ignited intense debate across the country.

The adoption of a same-faith ticket by the APC generated considerable tension within the polity, with many Christians interpreting the move as a deliberate attempt to marginalise their religious group or, more controversially, as a strategy aimed at the Islamisation of the Nigerian state. Consequently, the issue of religious representation in the 2023 election heightened inter-religious anxieties and threatened to polarise the country further, pitching adherents of one faith against another and exacerbating Nigeria's already fragile socio-political cohesion.

II. Statement of the Problem

Nigeria is widely recognised as a deeply divided society, structured along multiple and overlapping cleavages such as ethnicity, region, geopolitical zones, and religion. These fault lines profoundly shape political behaviour and competition. Consequently, the mobilisation of ethnic or religious identities as pathways to political power often assumes a sectarian character, with serious implications for the legitimacy, acceptance, and national appeal of candidates who emerge through such processes. Over time, this trend risks transforming elections from platforms for policy-based contestation into arenas dominated by primordial and identity-driven politics, thereby undermining democratic consolidation. Electoral politics in Nigeria have historically been influenced by religious considerations, but this influence became particularly pronounced during the 2023 presidential election, which sharply polarised the electorate along religious lines. Political elites and interest groups actively instrumentalised religious identity as a strategic resource for the acquisition and consolidation of political power. As a result, religion assumed a central role in campaign narratives, elite mobilisation, and voter alignment. Voting patterns during the 2023 presidential election reflected this deep religious cleavage. For instance, the Labour Party's presidential candidate, Peter Obi, was accused by some political actors of exacerbating religious divisions. The youth wing of the Arewa Consultative Forum alleged that Obi was engaging in ethnic and religious politics, citing his frequent interactions with Christian religious leaders and appearances at church-related events as evidence (Mohammed, 2023). Such accusations contributed to heightened suspicion and mistrust among different religious constituencies and intensified the already fragile intergroup relations within the polity.

More fundamentally, the 2023 presidential election generated unprecedented tension that many observers feared could threaten the corporate existence of the Nigerian state. Central to this tension was the decision of the All Progressives Congress (APC) to field a same-faith (Muslim–Muslim) presidential ticket, with Bola Ahmed Tinubu as its candidate. This decision was widely perceived, particularly among Christian groups, as an affront to Nigeria's delicate religious balance and an implicit attempt to marginalise

Christianity in national governance. Christian leaders and organisations framed the same-faith ticket as a calculated strategy aimed at the Islamisation of the Nigerian state. Prominent among the critics was the Forum of Northern Christians, led by a former Speaker of the House of Representatives, Mr. Yakubu Dogara. The Forum publicly reaffirmed its opposition to the same-faith ticket and declared its resolve not to relent. Dogara reportedly stated that “our position on same-faith ticket stands” and pledged to engage all presidential candidates across party lines to determine a choice that aligned with Christian interests (Olaiye, 2023). In furtherance of this position, Dogara held a series of closed-door consultations with Christian leaders from the 19 northern states and the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, as part of broader pre-election engagements. Similarly, the Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) issued strong statements condemning the APC’s same-faith ticket. According to the CAN Chairman in Kaduna State, Rev. John Hayab, the ticket constituted an attack on the Christian faith and an affront to the sensibilities of Nigerian Christians. He reiterated that CAN would not retreat from its opposition to what it described as the Muslim–Muslim ticket of the ruling party (Ibrahim, 2023). At the national level, the Christian Fellowship Association of Nigeria also denounced the ticket, characterising it as ill-conceived, provocative, and designed to sideline Christendom in Nigeria’s political space (Noah, 2023).

Scholarly attention to the intersection of religion and politics in Nigeria is not new. For instance, Kukah (1993) examined the historical roots of religious conflict and its implications for national integration, demonstrating how religious identity has been manipulated by political elites to consolidate power and exclude rivals. Similarly, Osaghae (2011) analysed identity politics in Nigeria and argued that religion, alongside ethnicity, has increasingly become a critical axis for political mobilisation, often deepening divisions and weakening state legitimacy. While these studies provide valuable insights into the role of religion in Nigeria’s political development, they largely focus on wider historical patterns or generalised identity politics. This study differs by offering a focused and contemporary analysis of the 2023 presidential election.

It is against this background that this study examines religion and politics in Nigeria, with emphasis on the 2023 Presidential election.

III. Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

1. Examine the dynamics, conduct, and outcomes of the 2023 Presidential election in Nigeria.
2. Analyse the role and impact of religion on voter behaviour, elite mobilisation, and electoral outcomes during the 2023 Presidential election in Nigeria.
3. proffer practical and policy-oriented measures for improving the conduct, credibility, and inclusiveness of elections in Nigeria.

CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

Religion

The notion of religion did not originally denote a distinct social category or cultural classification. Rather, it derives from the Latin term ‘religio’, which broadly connoted carefulness, scrupulous observance, or a deep sense of obligation. In this sense, religio was closely associated with conscientiousness, devotion, and moral duty, arising from taboos, vows, curses, or transgressions, even when such obligations were not directly linked to the worship of deities. In classical Western antiquity, and likely in many other societies, there was an awareness that different groups adhered to divergent forms of worship directed at different gods, often with mutually incompatible commitments. These distinctions frequently gave rise to social groupings that could compete or come into conflict with one another. Within this context, expressions such as ‘nobis religio’ were occasionally used to signify “our way of worship.” Despite this, religio possessed a wide range of meanings. Consequently, Augustine (1968) considered but ultimately rejected it as an appropriate abstract term for describing “the manner of worshipping God,” since the term, like other Latin expressions for “cult” or ‘service’, was equally applied to duties owed in both divine and human relationships (Augustine, 1976). Geertz (2017) conceptualised religion in relation to order, defining it as a

set of practices connected to beliefs about a general and overarching order of existence, one that is perceived as fundamental, pervasive, and unconditional. For Geertz, religious practices are those embedded in a culture's metaphysical worldview, that is, its understanding of the overall structure and meaning of reality. His conception of religion extends beyond theistic and polytheistic traditions, as earlier identified by scholars such as Herbert and Tylor, to include belief systems grounded in impersonal or natural principles. These include doctrines centred on karma, the Dao in Daoism, the Principle in Neo-Confucian thought, and the Logos in Stoicism. On this basis, Geertz also recognises Theravada Buddhism as a religion, given its emphasis on dependent co-origination as a foundational explanatory framework (Geertz, 2017). Galloway (2012) defines religion as humanity's faith in a power beyond the self, through which individuals seek emotional fulfilment, psychological stability, and meaning in life, expressed through acts of worship and service. This conception highlights religion as a form of religious consciousness, encompassing the cognitive, emotional, and volitional dimensions of human experience. Similarly, Miall (2013) describes religion as the finite human mind's awareness of its relationship to the absolute mind, thereby framing religion as a form of knowledge that connects human limitation with ultimate reality.

Politics

The concept of politics occupies a central place in the social sciences and has been interpreted in diverse ways by scholars. This multiplicity of meanings arises largely because politics, as an idea and a practice, evokes varied opinions, experiences, and sentiments. Almost everyone, by virtue of living within a society, tends to hold views on political matters, often assuming the role of an "expert." Moreover, politics is a universal phenomenon whose effects permeate all aspects of human life, shaping individual and collective experiences in profound ways.

Contemporary society is characterised by an increasing level of politicisation, where virtually all spheres of social existence fall within the domain of political decision-making. Government actions and inactions influence fundamental issues such as access to clean water, education, housing, marriage and divorce, employment, healthcare, and the provision of basic social amenities. Even the activities of international organisations and global institutions are embedded in political processes. This pervasive influence of politics lends credence to Aristotle's classical assertion that humans are by nature political animals. He further argued that social existence itself is inherently political, such that wherever two or more individuals interact, political relationships inevitably emerge. As people strive to secure their positions in society, safeguard personal interests, and influence others to accept their viewpoints, they invariably engage in political activity (Rodee et al., 2011).

Politics is therefore an omnipresent and unavoidable dimension of human existence. At its core, it refers to the conscious or unconscious struggle among individuals and groups to gain power, secure advantages, and realise interests within society. In this sense, politics has famously been described as the process of determining "who gets what, when, and how" (Lasswell, 1930). Similarly, Azikiwe (cited in Johnnie, 2005) views politics as an activity through which competing interests within a given territory are reconciled. From this perspective, politics encompasses not only competition over scarce resources but also decision-making processes and mechanisms for conflict resolution.

Other scholars conceptualise politics as the process through which members of a community deliberate on matters concerning the polis—the public realm—to pursue collective goals or the common good (Anifowose & Enemno, 1999). In a related vein, Curtis (2015) defines politics as an organised contest over power and its application, involving choices among competing values, ideas, interests, and demands. Politics, in this formulation, concerns how power is acquired, exercised, and regulated; the purposes for which it is deployed; the processes through which decisions are made; and the contextual factors that shape these decisions. This understanding underscores politics as a set of social relationships characterised by strategic manoeuvring and competition for authority.

Election

Elections constitute the formal mechanism through which individuals are chosen for public office or through which citizens approve or reject political proposals by casting their votes (Benoit et al., 2014). A

crucial distinction must be made between the form and the substance of elections. While the procedural aspects of elections may exist in some political systems, their substantive democratic content may be absent. This occurs in situations where voters are denied a free and genuine choice among at least two competing alternatives. As Benoit et al. (2014) observe, although the majority of countries conduct elections in a formal sense, many of these electoral processes lack competitiveness. In such contexts, opposition parties may be restricted or prohibited from participating, or the overall electoral environment may be severely constrained, thereby undermining the integrity of the process.

Within modern systems of representative government, elections occupy a central position. They are so closely associated with the emergence and consolidation of democratic political orders that they are widely regarded as the most critical indicator of the presence or absence of democracy in a given polity. Elections serve as the primary means through which citizens confer legitimacy on those who govern and hold political leaders accountable.

The International Encyclopedia of Social Sciences (2000) similarly defines elections as an institutionalised procedure through which members of an organisation or political community select a limited number of individuals to occupy positions of authority. This definition underscores the role of elections as structured decision-making processes designed to allocate power and leadership within both political and organisational settings.

IV. Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework adopted for this study is the elite theory propounded by Robert Michels, Gaetano Mosca and Vilfredo Pareto. The theory posits that power in the state or any organisation is exercised by a limited number of individuals or groups referred to as elites. In the view of Michels (1915), the ultimate fate of all organisations is to be run by a small minority or plural elites. In the view of Mosca (1939), human societies are divided into two major classes of people, namely, the rulers and the ruled. The ruling class is a minority group that monopolises power and enjoys the advantages that accrue from it. The ruled class (masses), on the other hand, constitutes the majority group but is directed and left in the hands of subsistence by the ruling class. Mosca (1939) went further to assert that power is always in the hands of an organised minority who have the authority and power over the majority by virtue of certain characteristics such as consensus on the basis of forms, cohesiveness and consciousness. Elite theory, therefore, views society as closed, pyramidal, unresponsive and composed of the few who rule and the many who are ruled. The dominant argument is that the large mass of the people is ignoble, not cohesive and not organised, and so is not competent or capable of exercising political power. Thus, political power is entrusted to the elite who are cohesive, organised, and competent or capable of exercising political power. This made Nna (2004 in Strickland et al., 1964) emphasise that authentic power resides in the hands of a very few people who occupy the leading positions in the corporation, the profession, the military and the executive branch of government.

According to Perry and Perry (2003), elitism is a theory which upholds that wealth, power, influence and prestige are held by a small number of individuals or groups who have achieved a higher degree of excellence in their endeavours. Elite theorists maintain that the consensus that supposedly exists in society is, in reality, established by the elites who are able to manipulate the masses through the mass media. The theory also asserts the existence of a multitude of interest groups whose interactions do not result in the diffusion of power. Here, society consists of a few who have power (elite) and the many who do not (masses). The elite hold key positions in society, such as those in the economy, military, politics, religion, and education, among other professions. The elite differ from the masses because they derive their value from their upper socio-economic class origin. Members share a common lifestyle and identify with others of the same background.

Applying the elite theory in understanding the influence of religion in Nigerian politics with regard to the conduct of the 2023 Presidential election, it becomes imperative to state that politics in Nigeria is being exploited by ethno-religious chauvinists in the Nigerian government and politics. Most political elites in Nigeria rely on ethnicity and religion as a tool to actualise their political goal. The political elite have enormous resources at their disposal with which they can manipulate the electorate. Also, because of the incentives attached to public offices in Nigeria, politics becomes a means to an end, to actualise the

economic goal of the political elite. It is the huge resources on display of the state that the elite struggle to control. The elite deploy religious sentiments for personal aggrandisement. This situation occasions violent competition, rivalry and drives to exterminate others in a zero-sum game of politicking and skewed governance.

V. Method and Materials

The study adopted the historical research design, which is particularly suitable for examining political developments and electoral processes over time. The use of the historical method helped to minimise researcher bias and subjectivity, as it relies largely on already documented events, records, and interpretations rather than personal observation or opinion. By drawing on established sources, the study ensures a more objective and systematic analysis of the subject matter. The research is based entirely on secondary sources of data. These data were obtained from official records of the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) and documented materials from registered political parties in Nigeria. In addition, relevant information was drawn from scholarly books, academic journals, magazines, and other credible published materials. The combination of official electoral data and scholarly literature provided a comprehensive and reliable basis for analysing the 2023 presidential election and the role of religion in Nigeria's electoral politics.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Dynamics, Conduct, and Outcomes of the 2023 Presidential Election in Nigeria

Nigeria conducted its seventh Presidential and National Assembly (NASS) elections in February 2023 since the country returned to democratic rule on May 29, 1999. This began with preparation for the Presidential elections by the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC). INEC began preparations for the 2023 general elections well ahead of time, building on the lessons learned from previous elections. The commission adopted several key measures to improve transparency, credibility, and public trust. One of the major steps was the enactment of the Electoral Act 2022, which introduced several reforms, including the legal backing for electronic transmission of results, early release of election funds, and timelines for party primaries and campaign periods (INEC, 2023). The Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) conducted a nationwide Continuous Voter Registration (CVR) exercise between June 2021 and July 2022, during which millions of eligible Nigerians either registered for the first time or updated their voter information. To enhance efficiency and reduce bottlenecks in the registration process, INEC introduced the INEC Voter Enrolment Device (IVED). In preparation for the election, the Commission also undertook the nationwide distribution of Permanent Voter Cards (PVCs) to registered voters, while simultaneously encouraging civic participation and addressing the problem of voter apathy. A major technological innovation in the 2023 general elections was the nationwide deployment of the Bimodal Voter Accreditation System (BVAS) for voter verification and electronic transmission of results, replacing the previously used smart card reader. This initiative was intended to curb electoral malpractices such as multiple voting, identity fraud, and result manipulation (INEC, 2023). In addition, INEC supervised party primaries, enforced campaign finance regulations, and accredited both domestic and international election observers to monitor the electoral process. The principal contenders in the 2023 presidential election were Bola Ahmed Tinubu of the All Progressives Congress (APC), Atiku Abubakar of the People's Democratic Party (PDP), Peter Obi of the Labour Party (LP), and Rabiu Musa Kwankwaso of the New Nigeria Peoples Party (NNPP).

Although the 2023 presidential election was characterised by certain irregularities, local and international observers generally assessed the process as relatively free, fair, and credible (Habib, 2023; Premium Times, 2023). The distribution of votes and National Assembly seats among multiple political parties reflected a competitive electoral environment. Compared to previous election cycles, particularly those marked by widespread violence and significant loss of life (Sanni, 2019), the 2023 elections recorded fewer incidents of violence and lower casualty figures (Folorunsho-Francis et al., 2023). Nonetheless, notable shortcomings persisted throughout the electoral process (Akeaya-Inne, 2023; Acheampong, 2023; Ijaseun, 2023). According to Samson Itodo, Executive Director of Yiaga Africa, many of the risks identified in the Election Manipulation Risk Index (EMRI) materialised during the conduct of the elections (Itodo, 2023). These challenges were largely attributed to INEC's inability to fully deliver on its stated commitments and

effectively restrain politically motivated irregularities. The presence of these irregularities raised concerns about possible alterations of election results. In addition, the electoral outcomes revealed unexpected voting patterns, with both the declared winner and the runners-up securing victories in regions traditionally considered strongholds of opposing parties. All three major candidates recorded significant levels of support across diverse regions of the country. While the APC emerged victorious with a margin of fewer than two million votes, securing 8,794,726 votes and winning in 12 of Nigeria’s 36 states, the two main opposition parties, the PDP and the LP, collectively garnered over 13 million votes and won in 24 states. The table below presents a state-by-state breakdown of the results of the 2023 presidential election.

Table 1.1: State-by-state results of the 2023 Presidential election result

S/N	States	APC	PDP	LP	NNPP
1	EKITI	201,494	89,554	11,397	264
2	OSUN	343,945	354,366	23,283	713
3	KWARA	263,572	136,909	31,116	3,141
4	ONDO	369,924	115,463	4,405	930
5	OGUN	341,554	123,831	85, 829	2,200
6	OYO	449,884	182,977	99,110	4,095
7	ENUGU	4,772	15,749	428,640	1,808
8	LAGOS	572,606	75,750	582,454	8442
9	GOMBE	146,977	319,123	26,160	10,520
10	JIGAWA	421,390	386,587	1,889	98,234
11	ADAMAWA	182,881	417,611	105,648	8,006
12	KATSINA	482,283	489,045	6,376	69,386
13	NASARAWA	172,922	147,093	191,361	12,715
14	NIGER	375,183	284,898	80,452	21,836
15	BENUE	310,468	130,081	308,372	4,740
16	FEDERAL CAPITAL TERRITORY (FCT) ABUJA	90,902	74,194	281,717	4,517
17	AKWA IBOM	160,620	214,012	132,683	7,796
18	EDO	144,471	89,585	331,163	2,743
19	ABIA	8,914	22,676	327,095	1,239
20	KOGI	240,751	145,104	56,217	4,238
21	BAUCHI	316,694	426,607	27,373	72,103
22	PLATEAU	307,195	243,808	466,272	8,869
23	BAYELSA	42,572	68,818	49,975	540
24	KADUNA	399,293	554,360	294,494	92,969

25	KEBBI	248,088	285,175	10,682	5,038
26	KANO	517,341	131,716	28,513	997,279
27	ZAMFARA	298,396	193,978	1,660	4044
28	SOKOTO	285,444	288,679	6,568	1,300
29	CROSS RIVER	130,520	95,425	179,917	1,644
30	DELTA	90,183	161,600	341,866	3,122
31	EBONYI	42,402	13,503	259,738	1,661
32	ANAMBRA	5,111	9,036	584,621	1,967
33	TARABA	135,165	189,017	146,315	12,818
34	BORNO	252,282	90,921	7,205	4,626
35	RIVERS	231,591	88,468	175,071	1,322
36	IMO	66,406	30,234	360,495	1,552
37	YOBE	151,459	198,567	2,406	18,270
	Total	8,794,726	6,984,520.	6,101,533	1,496,687

Source: Adapted from Eze C. C. & Karibi-Botoye Q. I. (2024)

The table above reveals the results of the 2023 Presidential election. As seen in the table, the candidate of the All Progressive Congress (APC), Bola Ahmed Tinubu, received a total number of 8,794,726 votes, followed by the candidate of the People’s Democratic Party (PDP), Atiku Abubakar, who came second with a total score of 6,984,520. While the candidate of the Labour Party (LP), Peter Obi, came third with a total score of 6,101,533. Similarly, the candidate of the New Nigerian People’s Party (NNPP) received 1,496,687 total votes. Further details regarding the votes received by each candidate can be seen in Table 1.1. A central issue arising from the 2023 presidential election is the highly fragmented distribution of votes and the absence of a decisive majority for the declared winner. Bola Ahmed Tinubu’s electoral victory was achieved without an overwhelming mandate, a circumstance that has generated significant debate regarding the perceived legitimacy of his presidency. This concern is further compounded by Nigeria’s longstanding condition as a deeply polarised society, marked by enduring divisions along ethnic, religious, and regional lines (Mustapha, 2002; Agbiboa & Okem, 2011). Beyond the traditional axes of religion and ethnicity that shaped the 2023 Presidential election, a new and increasingly influential category of political actors emerged: young Nigerians between the ages of 18 and 35. This demographic, driven by dissatisfaction with governance, economic hardship, and declining social welfare, has become more politically assertive in demanding systemic change. Although Nigerian youths have long been characterised as a latent source of social unrest, their political visibility and mobilisation have been significantly amplified through the use of digital technologies and social media. The coordinated nationwide protests against police brutality under the #EndSARS movement in 2020 exemplify this heightened civic engagement and collective resistance to state excesses.

A substantial proportion of the youth population, particularly in southern Nigeria, actively participated in the #EndSARS protests, and evidence suggests that many within this group subsequently supported Peter Obi, the Labour Party’s presidential candidate, during the 2023 elections (Obadare, 2023; Adeoye, 2023). Obi secured 6,101,533 votes, emerging victorious in 11 states as well as the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja. Notably, he also won in Lagos State, Nigeria’s economic hub and a traditional stronghold of Bola Tinubu. Meanwhile, Atiku Abubakar, the People’s Democratic Party (PDP) candidate and first runner-up, garnered 6,984,520 votes nationwide. The extensive dispersion of votes across candidates and regions, coupled with Tinubu’s receipt of only 36.6 per cent of the total 24,025,940 votes cast, underscores the absence of a broad-based electoral mandate. Furthermore, the outcome has been vigorously contested by the runners-up and their supporters, who together represent nearly 15 million voters—approximately 62 per cent of the total votes cast. These factors collectively raise critical questions about the depth of popular consent underpinning Tinubu’s victory and, by extension, the overall legitimacy of his presidency in a

politically fragmented and polarised Nigeria. INEC adjudged the 2023 Presidential election to be ‘free, fair and credible’ and urged aggrieved parties to approach the courts to ventilate their concerns and wait for the matter to be resolved (Amodu 2023). Without IReV working fully, the declared results were not accepted by the political parties and many members of the public, challenging the legitimacy of INEC’s results and questioning the emergence and Presidency of Bola Tinubu. The litigations against Tinubu’s mandate were put to rest following the affirmation of Tinubu’s victory by the Supreme Court.

The Role and Impact of Religion on Voter Behaviour, Elite Mobilisation, and Electoral Outcomes during the 2023 Presidential Election in Nigeria

By constitutional provision, Nigeria prohibits the adoption of any religion as a state religion, a principle that has often led to its classification as a secular state. In this context, secularism is commonly understood to imply the separation of religion from public affairs and the confinement of religious practice to the private sphere. However, characterising Nigeria as a fully secular state is overly simplistic, given the pervasive and visible influence of religion on political life. Consequently, scholars have offered alternative descriptions of the Nigerian state, variously referring to it as “partially secular,” “non-secular,” or “multi-religious” (Oshewolo & Maren, 2015). In practice, religion—often intertwined with ethnicity—exerts considerable influence on political behaviour, particularly voting patterns. Although successive governments have consistently urged citizens to prioritise national unity over religious and ethnic loyalties, electoral success in Nigeria remains largely dependent on securing the support of one’s religious and ethnic constituencies. The 2023 Nigerian presidential election, held on 25 February 2023, was conducted to elect the President and Vice President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. The election was won by Bola Ahmed Tinubu, a former Governor of Lagos State and candidate of the ruling All Progressives Congress (APC), who secured 8,794,726 votes. He was followed by Atiku Abubakar of the People’s Democratic Party (PDP), a former Vice President, who polled 6,984,520 votes. Religion played a significant role in shaping the electoral process and outcomes, as voting behaviour during the election largely reflected ethnic and religious alignments.

The composition of the presidential tickets further underscored the salience of religion in the 2023 contest. The APC presented a Muslim–Muslim ticket, with Bola Ahmed Tinubu, a Muslim from the South, and Kashim Shettima, a Muslim from the North. In contrast, the PDP adopted a religiously balanced ticket, fielding Atiku Abubakar, a Muslim from the North, alongside Ifeanyi Okowa, a Christian from the South. Similarly, the Labour Party (LP) sought religious and regional balance by presenting Peter Obi, a Christian from the South, with Yusuf Datti Baba-Ahmed, a Muslim from the North. Given that the outgoing President, Muhammadu Buhari, was a Muslim from Northern Nigeria, Tinubu’s victory resulted in the succession of one Muslim president by another. In a deeply divided society such as Nigeria, this outcome intensified scrutiny of the APC’s candidate selection strategy. The party’s Muslim–Muslim ticket attracted widespread criticism for allegedly disregarding Nigeria’s religious sensitivities. The Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN), the apex body representing Christians in the country, argued that the prevailing socio-political conditions made a same-faith ticket inappropriate and urged Nigerians to either accept or reject it through the electoral process (Musa, 2023). Similarly, the Catholic Bishop of Sokoto Diocese, Matthew Kukah, condemned the decision as unacceptable. Northern Christian leaders within the APC described the ticket as a manifestation of insensitivity to Nigeria’s religious diversity, while protests by some northern Christians in Abuja characterised it as an affront to their faith (Musa, 2023). Even Atiku Abubakar, the PDP presidential candidate, publicly acknowledged that the APC’s decision was ill-suited to Nigeria’s plural context. In response, the APC maintained that its choice prioritised competence, performance, and pragmatism over identity politics (Musa, 2023).

Despite its public downplaying of religious considerations in candidate selection, the APC appeared to actively seek religious balance during its campaign activities. Notably, allegations that the party hired individuals posing as Christian bishops during the unveiling of Tinubu’s running mate further fuelled outrage within Christian communities. In contrast, the PDP largely maintained a secular posture by balancing regional, ethnic, and religious factors in its ticket composition and exercising caution on religiously sensitive issues. However, Atiku Abubakar’s decision to delete social media posts condemning the killing of Deborah Samuel—a Christian accused of blasphemy—following threats from Islamist groups to withdraw support, revealed the strategic importance of religion in the electoral contest (Musa, 2023).

Moreover, the PDP's nomination of a Fulani Muslim to succeed another Fulani Muslim president after eight years in office also reignited religious and ethnic sentiments.

Although the Labour Party was widely perceived as relatively cautious in its handling of religious issues, Peter Obi was not exempt from religious framing by political opponents. Supporters of the APC and PDP criticised his frequent visits to Christian congregations, portraying him as a "Christian candidate" or "crusade mobiliser" in an attempt to weaken his appeal among Muslim voters (Adebayo, 2023). In July 2022, Obi's image was controversially printed on a Muslim prayer mat by a purported support group, an act widely condemned as offensive, which prompted a formal apology from him. These incidents highlight the depth of religious sensitivities in Nigeria's political landscape and the necessity of navigating them with caution. Table 1.1 revealed the total number of votes received by each of the Presidential candidates during the 2023 election. The table depicts the voting pattern from each of the states, which reflects religious and ethnic colouration. One can deduce from the table the voting pattern of the electorates during the Presidential election. The influence of religion on the outcome of the 2023 Presidential elections can be deduced from the table. The influence of religion on the voting pattern, for instance, the LP candidate garners more votes in Christian-dominated States and areas like the Federal Capital Territory (Abuja), Nasarawa and Plateau states, etc. In Nasarawa, he polled 191,361 votes against those of APC, 172,922 votes and 147,093 by PDP. Also, the other two candidates that were Muslim won more votes in Muslim dominated States like Kogi, Niger, Kano and Katsina, etc. For instance, in Katsina State, the PDP candidate pulled 489,045 votes, the APC 482,283, while the LP received 6,367. Also in Kogi State, APC: 240,751 votes, PDP: 145,104 votes, while LP: 56,217. The table contains further details on the influence of religion during the 2023 Presidential election. All these have implications for the outcome of the electoral process and good governance.

VII. Conclusion

In the Western world, the effect of religion is not as pronounced as it is in Africa. In Nigeria, for example, the choice of who becomes the President of Nigeria is often decided by a group, comprising the retired generals, traditional rulers and the religion that such a candidate professes. It is the preferred candidate of this group that subsequently emerges as the winner in every election. Therefore, one tends to wonder what is democratic about the Nigerian democracy, where religious doctrine plays a significant role in determining the choice of who becomes President. Ideally, it is the party executive that should organise the primaries where the most deserving candidates within the party are elected to contest in the main elections. This is not the practice in Nigerian democracy.

It thus appears that the Nigerian electorate has no choice for now of who becomes the President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, so long as religion remains the major consideration in Nigerian politics. It could be recalled that Chief Enahoro evolved the ideology of the six geo-political zones to minimise the negative effects of the north and south dichotomy in Nigerian politics. The present political arrangement does not appear to have made room for a fair representation by the six geo-political zones in the office of the President of Nigeria. Religion, as in times past, will shape the build-up to and outcome of the 2027 Presidential elections. The risk of States and geopolitical zones voting along sectarian lines is high. This may, however, lead to heightened religious sensitivities that may escalate existing tensions and fragilities. But these can be averted if the winning candidate offers guarantees and accommodates the religious fears of other faiths.

VIII. Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The Federal government should adopt a model where the office of the President of Nigeria will be rotated among the six geo-political zones as was earlier recommended by Chief Anthony Enahoro in the 1960s.
2. Government and civil society organisations should intensify voter education campaigns that emphasise the importance of competence, policies, and national unity over religious affiliation when choosing leaders.

3. Nigerian government should create a public-facing, non-partisan digital platform (possibly by INEC or civil society) that profiles candidates based on experience, public service record, integrity, and policy plans, excluding religious affiliation.

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